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The Psychosocial Adjustments of Broken Home Children and their Academic Performance in Select Secondary Schools in Marawi City

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Abstract.

This study aimed to understand the psychosocial adjustments and academic performance of children from broken homes in selected secondary schools in Marawi City during the 2018–2019 school year, as well as the variables that influenced these responses. Adolescents who experience parental separation often encounter numerous academic and emotional challenges; hence, this study aimed to explore how they cope and continue to perform academically. The study employed a cross-sectional survey and evaluation research design, utilizing both qualitative and quantitative approaches. A researcher-made questionnaire, validated by experts in the field of education, was administered to 151 respondents from eight selected public and private secondary schools in Marawi City. The findings revealed that most respondents were female, aged 17 and above, with parents who were separated and had a low family income. Respondents often resorted to emotional coping, such as finding time to be happy, remaining hopeful, and praying. They sometimes adjusted socially by maintaining friendships. In terms of academic performance, they showed motivation to finish their studies, regular attendance, and satisfactory CGPA levels. The study concludes that faith in God, emotional stability, and support from peers and family significantly contribute to the ability of children from broken homes to cope positively and perform well academically.

Keywords: Psychosocial Adjustment, Academic Performance, Children from Broken Homes, Parental Separation, Coping Strategies and Mechanisms